

Scientific Data Repository-related Policies: Mexico

Version 1

**International
Science Council**

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About the World Data System:

Founded in 2008, the [World Data System](#) (WDS) is an affiliated body of the International Science Council (ISC). Its mission is to enhance the capabilities, impact, and sustainability of its member repositories and data services by fostering trusted communities of scientific data repositories. The WDS also aims to strengthen the entire lifecycle of data management, ensuring that high-quality data supports first-class research output. Additionally, it advocates for accessible data along with transparent and reproducible science.

About the WDS series on Scientific Data Repository-related Policies:

The World Data System (WDS) [Policy Series](#) reviews country-specific policies related to the governance of scientific data repositories at the national level. Documenting these policies comprehensively is critical to fostering global collaborations and advancing science for the common good.

To this end, WDS is committed to maintaining and continually updating a list of national Open Science policies pertaining to data repositories. Additionally, WDS will host periodic webinars featuring experts from multiple countries to discuss their unique perspectives on Open Science Policies and how they impact data repositories. These sessions aim to inform researchers and policymakers on how to navigate international policy landscapes effectively.

In developing this Open Science Policy Series, WDS's goal is to create avenues for sharing knowledge and enhancing global scientific collaboration efforts. Ultimately, we hope this approach will promote transparency and ensure that science continues to work towards the common good by leveraging diverse international expertise. Note that the papers in this series will continually be updated with new and emerging information as it becomes available. The World Data System welcomes your input on these documents, including textual updates, references, policy suggestions, and link corrections, by emailing wds-ipo@utk.edu.

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Acronyms

CONACyT	National Council of Science and Technology (Consejo Nacional de Ciencia y Tecnología)
CONAHCyT	National Council of the Humanities, Science and Technology (Consejo Nacional de Humanidades, Ciencias y Tecnologías)
CONRICyT	National Consortium of Scientific and Technological Information Resources (Consortio Nacional de Recursos de Información Científica y Tecnológica)
CRMcyT	Classification of Mexican Journals of Science and Technology (Clasificación de Revistas Mexicanas de Ciencia y Tecnología)
CUDI	University Corporation for Internet Development (Corporación Universitaria para el Desarrollo de Internet)
Latindex	Sistema Regional de Información en línea para Revistas Científicas de América Latina, el Caribe, España y Portugal
LGMHCTI	General Law on Humanities, Sciences, Technologies, and Innovation (Ley General en Materia de Humanidades, Ciencias, Tecnologías e Innovación)
PRONACES	National Strategic Programs (Programas Nacionales Estratégicos)
Redalyc	Network of Scientific Journals from Latin America and the Caribbean, Spain, and Portugal (Red de Revistas Científicas de América Latina y el Caribe, España y Portugal)
REMERI	Mexican Network of Institutional Repositories (Red Mexicana de Repositorios Institucionales)
SciELO	Scientific Electronic Library Online
SECIHTI	Secretariat of Science, Humanities, Technology, and Innovation (Secretaría de Ciencia, Humanidades, Tecnología e Innovación)

Introduction

The World Data System (WDS) Policy Series reviews country-specific policies related to the governance of scientific data repositories at the national level. Documenting these policies comprehensively is critical to fostering global collaborations and advancing science for the common good. To this end, WDS is committed to maintaining and continually updating a list of national Open Science policies related to data repositories.

In Mexico, the importance of Open Science is highlighted as a key element for consolidating policy in the fields of Science, Humanities, Technology, and Innovation. This is achieved through the universal allocation of scholarships for postgraduate studies, the development of basic science projects with a focus on social inclusion and regional and local impact; whose results are publicly available, free, and digital, advancing towards universal access to knowledge as a human right recognized in the country's political Constitution (Vázquez, 2023).

Through agreements and other collaboration instruments, efforts are made to generate and disseminate knowledge and open science that contribute to ensuring the full and effective exercise of the human right to science, benefiting the Latin American and Caribbean region.

The General Law on Humanities, Sciences, Technologies, and Innovation, effective from May 2023, validates the human right to science by applying the principles of universality, interdependence, indivisibility, and progressiveness. The goal is for everyone to have access to the benefits of scientific development and technological innovation. To ensure the exercise of this human right, the capacities and infrastructures of the public sector in humanities, sciences, technologies, and innovation are made available to the population. Their use and exploitation are subject to public interest.

Scientific Data Repository-related Policies

The policies related to scientific data repositories specific to Mexico include:

- **Public Policy on Open Science**

To update and continue its management framework, the National Council of Science and Technology (CONACyT) reviewed its current guidelines in November 2015 and advanced in the Public Policy on Open Science. In addition to the previously established Repository Program, it included the programs for Public Communication of Science, Journals, the National Consortium of Scientific and Technological Information Resources, Connectivity, and the Integrated System of Scientific Information and Technological Development (CONACyT, 2017).

Since 2010, the National Consortium of Scientific and Technological Information Resources (CONRICYT) has been formed. Universities and public research institutions have participated in the Open Access movement since then, mainly to improve access to electronic publications (CONAHCyT, n.d.).

Through the Journals Program of the Open Science Policy, the Classification System of Mexican Journals of Science and Technology (CRMcyT System) was established. By registering and periodically evaluating scientific journals edited in Mexico, whether in electronic or printed format, it aims to improve their quality, visibility, and impact (CONACyT, n.d.).

The communication network called Nicté has been strengthened through the Connectivity Program. It continues to support broadband interconnection between universities and research centers with specialized education, research, and training networks, both nationally and internationally, to ensure frontier research generation (CUDI, n.d.).

On June 9, 2017, the General Guidelines for Open Science were formally issued (CONACyT, 2017b). These guidelines establish that the fundamental principles of Open Science are maximum openness, maximum capture, knowledge transfer and collaboration, maximum ease of access, minimal or no cost, respect for national security, intellectual property, confidentiality and data reservation, protected secrets, among other rights.

General Law on Humanities, Sciences, Technologies, and Innovation (LGMHCTI) CONAHCyT (an acronym resulting from including Humanities in the sector authority's name since 2022) and the Federal Government considered updating the legal framework in the sector. Thus, the new LGMHCTI was published in the Official Gazette of the Federation on May 8, 2023 (Chamber of Deputies, 2023).

This law includes a set of articles that validate open access to scientific results and benefits. Articles 10, 14, and 56 refer to universal and open access to scientific knowledge and its social benefits as well as cultural adequacy and environmental safety of its technological applications.

Articles 29, 33, and 47 refer to mechanisms ensuring public access to knowledge and results of state-funded research. Article 53 refers to Strategic National Programs (PRONACES), whose results must be made available to the public. It also references publication programs and open access to scientific information through agreements and inter-institutional arrangements.

In Title IV, regarding open access to Information, Chapter II refers to the National Information System and includes articles 57 to 63. These articles incorporate the relevance, value, and obligation to implement and consolidate various platforms for open access to research results through institutional repositories, the National Repository, the Information Ecosystems that concentrate information from PRONACES, and a transparency platform for sector management.

- Internal Regulations of the Secretariat of Science, Humanities, Technology, and Innovation (SECIHTI)

In January 2025, the internal regulations of the new SECIHTI were published, replacing the previous CONAHCyT. Its guidelines represent continuity in sector policy with programs such as National Laboratories that reinforce public scientific infrastructure and contribute to guaranteeing the principles of Open Science (Presidency of the Republic, 2025).

According to article 11 of the regulations, it is the responsibility of the Undersecretariat for Technological Development, Linkage, and Innovation to promote the quality of research, technological developments, social access to their benefits, and scientific and humanistic knowledge; for this purpose, it must establish strategies for open access to knowledge resulting from state funding.

Article 20 establishes that the General Directorate of Public Research Centers and National Laboratories must stimulate the establishment of open access strategies for all results and materials developed in the National System of Public Centers; among others, it consolidates the National Laboratories Programs and National and Institutional Repositories.

Furthermore, article 21 specifies that the General Directorate of Priority Programs, through PRONACES, must promote research, dissemination, and development of scientific projects, as well as open access to information derived from these activities. For this purpose, it establishes the implementation of National Information Ecosystems or other similar platforms in alignment with LGMHCTI.

According to article 22, the General Directorate of National Scientific Information Systems is responsible for coordinating the design and implementation of previously mentioned information systems and open access.

- Advances in Open Science in Mexico:
 - A. Around 70% of Higher Education Institutions have some type of repository or journal portal that mostly uses open infrastructures and open-source software, such as Dspace, Dataverse, OJS, or VIVO (Vázquez, 2022).
 - B. There is experience in open publications, such as REMERI (green route), Latindex, and Redalyc (diamond route).
 - C. The SciELO system develops a preprint repository and a data repository, which are not exclusive to journals included in the SciELO collections.

- Pending actions:
 1. Strengthen the Open Science Policy, especially aligning research support programs such as the SNI and editorial infrastructures with the principles of Open Science to promote their widespread application. Emphasis should be placed on the acceptance of preprints, open data deposits, and open review (Zetter, Díaz, Garrido, Gallegos, & Rivera, 2024).
 2. Continuity in the national sector strategy for strengthening Institutional and/or Data Repositories and the National Repository.
 3. Promote citizen Open Science projects.
 4. Align the regulations of Public Higher Education and Research Institutions with the principles of Open Science.

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